

Effect of Addition of Non-plastic Materials on the Rheological Behaviour of Clay Suspension

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Clay-water system appears to be interesting as the rheological behaviour is related to the stability of such suspensions. In the interpretation of rheological behaviour of clay suspension it has been agreed¹ that the cations and the anions present in the medium affect this property to a significant extent. Van Olphen² summarised the type of particle-particle interaction occurring in aqueous phase during interaction with electrolytes. The present communication reports the findings on the effect of gradual addition of solid additives such as quartz and felspar, on the rheological parameters of two clay suspensions.

Results and Discussion

The flow behaviour of 35% kaolin and 15% bentonite suspension lies in the non-Newtonian region as revealed from the existence of yield value (Table 1). Both the clay minerals exhibited reduction of yield

change of plastic viscosity of bentonite were not identical.

The interaction of felspar was quite different from that of quartz. Unlike quartz, which is pure SiO₂, felspar contains Na₂O in the composition which is normally hydrolysed to a limited extent in aqueous phase. The stabilisation effect of alkali due to controlled release was visualised from the diffuse nature of the yield value curve (Fig. 1). From the nature of the individual curves for kaolin and bentonite with respect to the changes of rheological parameters, the latter was found to be more active. This may be attributed to the higher cation exchange capacity of bentonite. When the same kaolin suspension was interacted with the mixture of quartz and felspar the nature of change of rheological parameters was more or less identical to those obtained with felspar alone (Fig. 1). The initial reduction of both yield value and plastic viscosity might be due to colloid-chemical interaction of clay with the liberated alkali from the felspar lattice. Bentonite exhibited identical relationship to kaolin upto addition of 4 g mixture of non-plastic additives (Fig. 2). After that more than one inflexion points

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF RAJMAHAL CHINA CLAY AND TEENPAHARI BENTONITE IN Na-FORM

Property	Rajmahal china clay	Teenpahari bentonite
SiO ₂ (%)	46.9	51.3
Al ₂ O ₃ (%)	39.2	27.3
Fe ₂ O ₃ (%)	0.65	1.41
MgO (%)	—	1.36
Loss on ignition (%)	12.7	14.9
CEC meq/100 g	8.2	97.2
DTA peak temp. (°C)	600 (endo) 990 (exo)	155 (endo) 365 (exo) 940 (exo)
Surface area (m ² g ⁻¹)	25	102
Yield value (dyne cm ⁻²)	59.7 at 35% concn.	0.280 at 15% concn.
Plastic viscosity (po:se)	0.814 at 35% concn.	0.031 at 15% concn.

value and plastic viscosity on addition of non-plastic materials. The changes of these parameters with gradual incorporation of the additives have been represented in Figs. 1 and 2. During initial addition of quartz, the yield value increased for both the clays upto a certain limit and then decreased although the path and the magnitude were different. The change was more prominent in bentonite upto 10 g addition. Kaolin showed very little change of yield value. The change of plastic viscosity on addition of quartz proceeded in a stepwise manner for kaolin. The inflexion points with respect to the

Fig. 1. Yield value and plastic viscosity relationship of 35% Na-kaolin suspension during interaction with non-plastic additive: (O) quartz, (Δ) felspar and (●) quartz+felspar.

Fig. 2. Yield value and plastic viscosity relationship of 15% Na-bentonite suspension during interaction with non-plastic additive: (○) quartz, (△) felspar and (□) quartz+felspar.

were observed. In case of the mixed additives, the reaction was partly mechanical and partly chemical in nature. It is to be mentioned here that both the clays were taken in sodium form.

Thus, it appears from the above results that plasticity of clay masses is influenced by the alignment of plate-like clay particles. It has been shown that if a plastic mass is continuously subjected to alternate tensional and compressive stresses, a loosening of structure develops and eventually small stresses produce large deformation. This phenomenon is attributed to the gradual orientation of the mineral phase. Although the ions liberated from the particular non-plastic additive influenced the colloidal behaviour of clay suspension the positioning of the non-plastic additives in the oriented clay suspension and its ability to remain in that state also contributed to a greater extent.

The yield value and the plastic viscosity changes are related to the orientation of the clay and associated particles in the aqueous phase. Sedimentation behaviour of the suspension was also studied in presence of non-plastic additives and the curves did not exhibit significant change (Fig. 3). This indicated the greater stabilisation of the suspension.

Conclusion: The influence of the non-plastic additives like quartz and felspar to kaolin and bentonite suspension was significantly reflected in the

Fig. 3. Sedimentation characteristics of clay suspension: (○) quartz, (●) felspar and (△) quartz+felspar.

reduction of both plastic viscosity and yield value. Unlike quartz which is inert with respect to chemical reactivity, felspar exhibited enhanced stability due to controlled liberation of alkali by hydrolysis.

Experimental

Rajmahal china clay and Teenpahari bentonite were purified, fractionated, converted into Na-form and stored by the usual procedure³. The purified clays of selected size fraction behaved in a non-Newtonian manner at a concentration of 35% (w/v) for kaolin and 15% (w/v) for bentonite. At these concentrations they were interacted with different proportions of quartz and felspar under equilibrium condition at room temperature (30–32°).

The rheological measurement of the clay suspensions was carried out in a McMichael cup and bob viscometer. The most important parameters for non-Newtonian rheology, i.e. yield value and plastic viscosity, were determined utilising the well known Reiner-Riwlin equation for plastic flow⁴. Sedimentation studies of clay suspensions in presence of the above additives were also carried out at 30–32° allowing 24 h settling time.

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